

THE IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZING INTERACTIVE CLASSES USING MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article talks about easy and effective ways to learn and teach a foreign language. The article deals with implementation of interactive forms of teaching foreign language and efficiency of foreign language lessons using interactive methods in educational institutions.*

Keywords: *multimedia tools, activities, innovative technology, different methods, free-thinking, educational process.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МУЛЬТИМЕДИА ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассказывается о простых и эффективных способах изучения и преподавания иностранного языка. В статье речь идет о внедрении интерактивных форм обучения иностранному языку и эффективности проведения уроков иностранного языка с использованием интерактивных методов в общеобразовательных учреждениях.*

Ключевые слова: *мультимедийные средства, деятельность, инновационная технология, разные методы, свободомыслие, образовательный процесс.*

INTRODUCTION

We know that this year, under the chairmanship of our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the system of teaching foreign languages, foreign language teachers and students from 2021 at the video selector meeting dedicated to improvement it was emphasized that the requirement to have a national and international certificate should be introduced. This puts a huge responsibility on their shoulders. Now, instead of traditional teaching methods, we should organize the teaching process based on interactive methods using new ICT. This training is also a requirement of the times, and the teacher has to work more and more on a little. While paying attention to new methods of teaching in the article, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the type and effectiveness of these methods.

OBJECT OF RESEARCH

It should be noted that new methods and requirements for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers have been developed in our republic in accordance with the recommendations of the pan-European framework. According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques.

CD players are available. The use of these technical tools is alien to students makes the language learning process more interesting and effective. Advanced methods serve as a compound in the thorough mastery of a foreign language. One such method is the use of role-playing games in the teaching process. Role playing games are real is to use different situations in our life in the

process of learning a foreign language. This method is used in the course of the lesson helps to create a language environment. In the process of participating in these role-playing games, students learn to think, themselves they learn to freely express their emotional states in a foreign language. Preparation for role-playing games in the process, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. Make a mistake and that's it error correction also helps language learning and teaches students correct pronunciation. Lesson in the process of using role-playing games, all students are actively participating in the lesson at the same time provides them. In addition, role-playing games make students interested in learning a foreign language increases and creates a lively, cheerful atmosphere for the lesson process. And this is foreign language lessons serves to increase efficiency.

SUBJECT OF RESEARCH

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active movement of the student in the educational process is envisaged is caught. In conclusion, as a result of using innovative methods in English classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student is thoroughly prepared for the lessons seeks to see. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. Education system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers ways to effectively use innovative technologies. We can add more as we develop more. Every day, every hour, news and changes in the field of science are presented to the people of science sets new tasks. Using modern technologies in teaching foreign languages educating the young generation requires knowledgeable and talented specialists. Today's the need of the time - potential, at the same time, modern knowledge, computer technology, multimedia is to raise children who have thoroughly mastered the means and know a foreign language perfectly. That's it methodological preparation of the foreign language teacher is of particular importance. Fanny is good along with knowledge, information that is widely introduced into the educational process today.

THE PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

A teacher who fully uses the possibilities of technology is good at his work can achieve results. Children today are in a highly networked environment through the media they are growing up. Current global processes and new information technologies are also spoken by children leads to a change in attitude. Even the daily life of small children and in many places under the influence of media and multiculturalism and multilingualism is passing Cultural diversity and linguistic diversity of the world we live in not only in kindergartens and schools, but even before that, directly with the family and the child. It is manifested in the relationships in the environment. Based on this, the modern teacher is advanced pedagogic and information communication technologies along with deep knowledge of science should be informed, able to use the Internet and computer capabilities at a low level.

In addition, each lesson is made live through multimedia tools, didactic materials, visual aids, interesting organization serves the effectiveness of education. Including: Teacher in the classroom can use:

- Presentations or web presentations created by teacher-students.
- Electronic encyclopedias.

- Electronic textbooks. (From the student first observing a training course or carrying out a virtual experiment based on the acquired knowledge, and then the knowledge it is suggested to go through the software management system).

- Interactive trainings

- To the teacher form the questions of the assignments and log the score given by the computer test constructors that allow input. On the use of information technologies and the following examples of high productivity can be given to the main types of lessons:

- From the computer lessons using a demo mode using a projector / or a lesson using an interactive whiteboard

The main groups of tasks solved using multimedia are:-

*to support students' academic work.

*ensuring authentic communication with native speakers

* providing access to all participants of the educational process from rapidly growing information funds stored in centralized information systems;

* ensuring mutual cooperation of teachers, exchange of pedagogical experience and didactic materials. In particular, learning and teaching foreign languages through the Internet not only allows people who speak different languages to get in touch with each other, but also to get to know countries and people's lifestyles.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that ideas are exchanged using these methods. And this is the speech of the student effectively affects the development of activity and independent thinking

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